

COMPARISON AND THEIR USE IN PROVERBS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a brief overview of the linguistic origin of comparison and its usage in the fields of linguistics as a stylistic feature. Moreover, by the helping of the article, individual can understand the notion of comparison as well as description of its role in linguistics. Due to exploring the task, proverbs are taken as an object to work on them and exploring how the stylistic feature (comparison) is used on them.

Materials: *as a material of the article, proverbs are chosen. The reason is why they are taken as an object is that proverbs have long been the units that have preserved the richness and language devices of languages for centuries. In which this stylistic device is very common. For a proverb made by the method of comparison not only attracts the attention of the listener, but also gives him a broader understanding.*

Research methods. *Comparative – historical method is found beneficial to identify the optimal information about units of proverbs and their usage in a language. Another beneficial method is observation that allows explorers to collect information about an object.*

Results and discussions. *By the helping of the article, it is provided a wealth of information based on comparison and its usage on proverbs. As well as the reader can get acquainted with the linguistic analysis of the proverbs given below.*

Conclusion. *At the end of the article, the researcher is able to witness that the linguistic theoretical foundations of the comparison by giving examples in the shape of proverbs with translations in both languages: Uzbek and English languages, formed on the basis of observations and its importance in linguistics have been clarified.*

Comparison is the basis of human thinking, a way of knowing the world and human being, a creative force that enriches the language with new words and constructions, bright, very common and productive method of creating an image and artistic expression. Comparison actualizes the meaning statements and adds a personal, subjective component to it, it used to attract attention, influence participants communications. In addition, comparison is also an evaluative tool, facilitating the expression of the speaker's attitude to the transmitted information. In the article under review, comparison is considered as linguistic unit, which is a comparison of two objects, having a common feature, in order to clarify their similarities or differences, as well as establishing a change in the intensity of the attribute of the object and the degree this change, expressed by means of different levels of the language

(lexical, phraseological, derivational, morphological, syntactic). The problem of developing the topic of comparison in linguistics devoted to a significant number of works. Comparison importance as a grammatical phenomenon (V.V. Babaysteva, N.S. Valgina, S. M. Kolesnikova, V.M. Ogoltsev, A.F. Prtaykina, A.G. Rudnev, N. U. Shvedova, N.A. Shirokova and others.), as a phenomenon of the semantic component of the language (U.D. Apresyan, and D. Aryutyunova, A. Verjbitskaya, I.V. Dmitriveskaya, L.A. Ivanova, U.P. Knayoz, L.P. Krisin and others.), Uzbek linguists also have paid their attention and done numerous researches on comparison, they are A. Abduazizov, I. Irisqulov, A. Amirova, S. Usmonov, S. Boymirzayeva, X, Ne'matov, I. Koduxov, A. Kondashov and others.

Comparison as a linguistic unit has its own special constructive features that distinguish it from other linguistic phenomena. In the ideal, full version, the comparison is a three-term structure that includes an object, a standard, and a comparison base. An object - Comparison is an object, phenomenon, action that is in the field of attention speaker and evaluated by him. The object of comparison can be expressed by the name noun: *eyes like stars*, pronoun: *me like my dad*, became a doctor, verb (participle, gerund): the runner *looked like a rat*, adverb: *dark as a forest*.

We know that comparison appears mostly in stylistic devices so that it is clear that there are some types of comparison, following:

- **Analogy** - Another umbrella term, similar to the definition of comparison, referring to any comparison that explores the similarities or differences between two things.
- **Juxtaposition** - Placing two concepts, characters, ideas, etc., near each other so that the reader makes comparisons between them and perhaps contrasts them as well.
- **Metaphor** - Comparing two things without the use of "like" or "as" asserting that one thing is another, such as "My love is an ocean."
- **Simile** - Comparing two things with the conjunction "like" or "as," such as "My love was like an ocean."
- **Pun** - Using comparison to creative cognitive links in a humorous way, for example, "I'm glad I know sign language, it's pretty handy."
- **Allegory** - An extended metaphor that carries throughout an entire piece of literature that compares the situation in the story to a real-life situation.

The most commonly used units of comparison are proverbs. A proverb is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon. She attracts close attention of scientists both for its form and content. "On the one hand, this is a phenomenon of language, similar to ordinary phraseological units, with on the other hand, these are logical units (judgments and inferences), and with third - artistic miniatures, in a bright chased form reflecting facts of living reality..."¹ These signs help to give a general definition of the proverb: A proverb is a popular evaluative statement-cliché moralistic semantics.² Most proverbs are directly metaphorical. In these proverbs, the conceptualization of reality is based on recategorization

¹ Юдина И.Ю. Структура и семантика английских пословиц и поговорок о любви // XXI век: итоги прошлого и проблемы настоящего: межвуз. сб. науч. трудов (международный выпуск). - Пенза: ПГТА, 2009. - №12-С.125-127.-0,2 п.л.

² Юдина И.Ю. Метафора В Английской Пословице. автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата филологических наук 10 янв 2013 москва-2012.

of linguistic units, the essence of which is interaction of two cognitive spheres as a result of conceptualization one category through another. Metaphor, using overlay of conceptual spheres, combines these spheres into a single mental space and, thereby, helps a person to know more about the represented concept, reinforcing its figurative aspect thinking potential.

Metaphor is the most common type of tropes in the system. Figurative means of language. It intersects with other stylistic techniques, but at the same time, somewhat different from them. So, extralinguistic foundations of metaphor are mediated, and metonymy completely based on them. Hyperbole is close to metaphor, but the purpose of metaphor is enrichment of the content of thought by its figurative expression, and hyperbole only enhances, emphasizes certain properties or features of the subject of thought. The main function of the grotesque is to create a comic effect, while a metaphor is intended to serve as an ornament to speech. Here are some more examples which comparison is used in proverbs:

Proverb which used comparison	Alternative variations in Uzbek language
<i>Honesty is the best policy</i>	<i>Halollik eng yaxshi siyosatdir</i>
<i>A good wife makes a good husband</i>	<i>Xotin yaxshi bo'lsa er yaxshi bo'ladi</i>
<i>An idle brain is the devil's workshop</i>	<i>Bo'sh miya shayton inidir</i>
<i>Laws catch flies, but let hornets go free</i>	<i>Qonun aybsizni ushlar, aybdor esa ozod</i>
<i>A tattler is worse than a thief</i>	<i>Chayqovchi o'g'ridan yomonroq</i>
<i>Faults are thick where love is thin</i>	<i>Sevgi bor joyda ayblar ko'rinmas</i>
<i>Many hands make light work</i>	<i>Ko'p bilan ishing yengil bitadi</i>
<i>Prayer is good, work is better</i>	<i>Diling ollohda qo'ling mehnatda bo'lsin</i>

Evaluative attitude expressed in the proverbs of the English language, allows you to divide proverbs into semantic classes. In these examples, we have identified the following semantic classes, reflecting the evaluative attitude to such socially significant concepts as *love, friendship, laboring, working, knowledge, learning, hometown, stupidity, family and family relationship*. According to the examples, all the proverb are constructed on the comparison with the one stylistic device called metaphor.

Direct meaning in proverbs with full rethought meaning can express some unreal fact, and the metaphor in such proverbs conveys their positive or negative evaluative meaning. So, the English proverb *Blind men can judge by colors* with completely rethought-meaning speaks of the character of a person. There is a person in it presented as a stubborn person who does not want to listen to the advice of others, always stands his ground, even if he is wrong. Such a disapproving characterization person gives the proverb a negative evaluative meaning. English proverbs with partially reinterpreted meanings can perceived in its direct meaning, and the metaphorical transfer of one or several components gives them additional meaning, expressing positive or negative evaluative meaning. For example, English proverb *A bad workman quarrels with his tools* has rethought component "tools" ("tools" in the literal sense). But thanks to the metaphor, this proverb acquires a negative evaluative meaning "*bilimsiz ishchi ishlashni bilmas.*" Along with the actual metaphor (tropes) characteristic of proverbs stylistic device is comparison (figure), expressive whose status, by definition, is close to a metaphor. In proverbs, comparison usually expressed with *better ... than ... or* in the form comparative contrasting nominations. **Metaphor** and **comparison**, within the framework of

the formal identifications and assimilations, in essence, express the equivalent meaning, while the **metaphor expresses a hidden comparison, and comparison - open**. These types of juxtaposition directly and directly express evaluative meaning of the proverb.

Coming to conclusion, the problem of speech variation, in particular occasional the use of proverbs is of great interest to phraseologists. Frequent the use of this or that proverb can lead to the loss of figuratively emotional and functional load, to the loss of expressiveness. As a result, the speaker-writer, and above all, the author-writer the desire to search for new expression and imagery of data is developing units, resulting in the emergence of occasional variants proverbs. Comparison is a fundamental tool which is used for making the proverbs attractive and meaningful by comparing one thing to the other one with utilizing stylistic devices and specific words that are able to be compared.

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